

Economic Sanctions as a Tool in International Relations: A Critical Analysis of its Conception, Implementation and Effective- ness in Zimbabwe 1996- 2008

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ABSTRACT

The last four years into the 2000 new millennium ushered in a new era of disbelief, discontent and despair in the eyes, on one hand, of Zimbabwean state as an actor in the international system, and on the other hand, of the international community. Some international actors chose (besides other forms altering the behavior, i.e. military force, political coercion, covert action and diplomatic persuasion) to impose sanctions on Zimbabwe citing misdeeds that the country was committing. Sanctions, as such, were targeted at altering the behavior of Zimbabwe as an actor in international relations to more desirable state of affairs from the point of view of the imposers. It is the purpose of this paper to analyse the justifications and implementation of sanctions as a tool of inducing change of behavior of international actors. It holds that, though the sanctions had a considerable impact on Zimbabwe, the intended objectives were not achieved. The short article, in the final analysis, seeks to investigate the factors that contributed to their failure from the perspectives of both the imposer and the target.

Keywords: Sanctions, European Union, International Relations, Multilateral Institutions, Zimbabwe.

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INTRODUCTION

As already mentioned, this article attempts to explore and draw attention to the implications and impact of sanctions regime on Zimbabwe's development. It questions the effectiveness of the current sanctions regime. The question of whether sanctions work has been the subject of considerable scholarly debate over the years. The principal argument is that, contrary to the common belief that sanctions can bring about the desired goals of compelling the government to act and behave in a particular manner, they are, in fact, missing their intended targets. Instead, they are hitting the poor, disempowering civil society and consequently threatening overall development process. The paper goes beyond the basic political assertions and considers at length whether or not the sanctions regime has itself become a threat to development in Zimbabwe.

THE CONCEPT OF ECONOMIC SANCTIONS

Traditionally, sanctions have taken the forms of arms embargo, imposition of trade and financial restrictions, interruption of relations by air and sea and diplomatic isolation. Sanctions are basically measures applied in response to perceived wrongdoing by a state. Put simply, a sanction can be either a punishment or permission. Economic sanctions can vary from imposing import duties on goods from, or blocking the export

of certain goods to the target country, to a full naval blockade of its ports in an effort to verify, and curb or bar specified imported goods. In essence, then, sanctions are used as a policy of segregation for political and economic isolation by the imposing entities.

According to Evans and Newnham (1990,79) economic sanctions are "a form of economic statecraft which involves the use of economic capability by an actor or a group of actors (the imposer) in a deliberately coercive manner to pursue certain policy goals." They generally noted that, "the Imposer will identify a certain actor or a group of actors (the Target) against which the sanctions will be directed. The reasons for sanctions is get the Target to behave in a more compliant and favourable way of the Imposer. The means used to secure this compliance will involve denying the target access to certain goods and services that are controlled by the Imposer". (Ibid). Thus, in economic sanctions the Imposer seeks to deliberately weaken the economy of the Target, either temporarily or permanently. Economic sanctions may be directed at the whole Target or at some section of the society within the target.

WHY SANCTIONS ON ZIMBABWE?

In Zimbabwe, the Western countries that enacted sanctions have interests that they want to attain. It is not so much about, what exist as conventional knowledge, abuse of human rights, lack of democracy and the rule of law but rather much about the West and their interest. According to Brath (2002):

The policies of Western capital in Zimbabwe relegated Zimbabwe to being a source of natural resources and raw materials, combined with a specialized agricultural economy based on cash crops for export – tobacco being the most important export crop – rather than diversified agricultural production that includes production of food for domestic consumption. These economic policies of Western capital were exacerbated by the Structural Adjustment Programme (s) of the IMF and the World Bank. ZANU-PF and Robert Mugabe have, until recently, been the "Quislings" of British and American transnational corporations. ZANU-PF sold out the Zimbabwean peasants and workers long ago when it agreed to the Lancaster Agreement that left the Zimbabwean economy and the arable land in the hands of domestic and transnational capitalists... Capital interests in Zimbabwe expected ZANU-PF to uphold the pilfering "rule of law" of the Lancaster Agreement. ZANU-PF "did the right thing" and stood with the dispossessed population of Zimbabwe. As a consequence of supporting the land seizures in Zimbabwe, ZANU-PF and Robert Mugabe have fallen out of favour with the British and American transnational corporations, as well as with the domestic capitalists in Zimbabwe – both Black and White.

For individual countries issue of interests have remained. For instance, according to White (2007), "The only things that the US is trying to recover in Zimbabwe are the economic interests of capital, and to maintain the presence of those interests in Zimbabwe. The objective is not "democracy" and "economic recovery" in Zimbabwe."

In this sense, sanctions in Zimbabwe that have tended to sacrifice the life of a whole people

for the sake of maintaining the strategic interests of a western state, would in no way be ethically justifiable. On the whole, the issue of human rights and democracy being cited become only smokescreens to cover up the real interests and objectives underlying the sanctions.

In no uncertain terms, sanctions in Zimbabwe have led to abuse of human rights, instead of solving the alleged problem in that regard. According to Hondora (2005) human rights ought to be understood in its rightful place or context. As he puts it:

A hierarchical order exists within human rights. Within this order, the right to life assumes primary importance. Rights such as those to health, peace and development can be derived from the right to life. These fundamental human rights, which are also fundamental economic and social rights, are the precondition for the validity of fundamental rights and freedoms...Sanctions which invalidate the fundamental economic and social rights of the population are problematic.

It thus follows that, from the point of view of international law, sanctions on Zimbabwe violated Paragraph. 1 of Article 54 of the First Additional Protocol to the Geneva Conventions, which notes that starvation of civilians as a method of warfare is prohibited. For Zimbabwe, the sanction had the net effect of affecting the common man in the street who has to bear with poor service provision, drastic shortages of basic commodities and much needed medical supplies.

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SANCTION REGIMEN

The application of sanctions in Zimbabwe can be divided into two categories, i.e. as it relates to individual countries on one hand, and multilateral institutions on the other. Pertaining to individual countries they took the form of targeted sanctions whereby certain individuals or organisations within a country are specifically focused upon using, for example, travel bans, asset freezing, and restricting them from accessing benefits from the international community. Here lie some of the contradictions; as most of the people targeted by sanctions are covered by state immunity whether the restrictions become legal under international [laws] generates some problems. Even if they succeed [and] the targeted people conduct business on behalf of the general populace of the country, restrictions will directly affect the running of the affairs of the state, hence upsetting security and development of the nation as a whole. It suffices to say that eventually it is the general citizens that suffer, while the intended targets escape the effect of the sanctions because they have the power and opportunities to do so. In actual fact they will be the only ones accessing the available resources for their survival.

To legalise implementing its sanctions against Zimbabwe, the United States of America enacted a legislation called the Zimbabwe Democracy Economic Recovery Act (ZIDERA) of 2001. Specifically,

Section 4(c) Subsection 1 allows US executive directors to each international financial institution to oppose the vote against any extension by the respective institution of any loan, credit, or guarantee to the Government of Zimbabwe; or any cancellation or reduction of indebtedness owed by the Government of Zimbabwe to the United States or any international financial institution. (<http://www.zimdaily.com/news/117/ARTICLE/1879/2007-07-19.html>).

In the case of Britain's sanction, a number of areas of cooperation have been affected. Britain has militarily stopped the support it has been giving to Zimbabwe, and special export arrangements of various commodities have also supposedly been affected.

Secondly, multilateral institutions have been part of the sanction regime, working together with individual countries. United State had continued to use institutions she has influence on to implement its sanction on Zimbabwe. According to Hondora (2005), through ZIDERA:

From the date of its promulgation, any Zimbabwe foreign currency loan application made to the IMF, World Bank, the African Development Bank, among others, stood to be scuttled by the US, directly through its vote or indirectly through its influence within the institutions. On the international credit markets, with its junk investment status, Zimbabwe became an untouchable, because of its loan defaults and also because of the natural consequences

following the promulgation of ZIDERA. It also meant that any loan application made by Zimbabwe to any multilateral or bilateral international lending agency would carry an exorbitantly high cost, if they were willing to do business at all. This economic cost is quantifiable. Further, the US position, expressed through ZIDERA, meant that Zimbabwe would be unable to reschedule repayments of its debts due to the multilateral lending agencies. Practically speaking, debts became due and payable. And this explains why Zimbabwe paid £120 million to the IMF, and could not reschedule its IMF debt. That is a quantifiable cost.

Britain, in its turn, has influenced the European Union to push its agenda and impose the sanction the country in a number of ways. The EU suspended and re-orientated of certain financial and development cooperation programmes with the Government of Zimbabwe.

In response to the land reform programme that came into force in 2000, sanctions have been imposed on Zimbabwe by multilateral financial institutions as well. They suspended all forms of balance of payments support, technical assistance, grants and infrastructural development flows to both government and private sectors and stopped all lending operations to the country (<http://www.zimdaily.com/news/117/ARTICLE/1879/2007-07-19.html>).

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF SANCTIONS

On the whole, the immediate consequence of eight years of sanctions has been a dramatic fall in living standards, the collapse of the infrastructure, and a serious decline in the availability of public services. While the longer-term damage to the fabric of society has yet to be assessed, economic disruption has already led to heightened levels of crime, corruption and violence. In general terms, according to Mugabe, *The challenges to the economy are being aggravated by declared and undeclared sanctions by the Western countries, resulting in the absence of balance of payments support, the stagnation in capital inflows and escalation in the prices of goods and services* (cited in Ruzvidzo 2007).

When we turn to analyse specific sectors in Zimbabwe, the hardest hit have been industries that are dependent on imports, whose production fell due to the lack of raw materials and semi-manufactured products, as did the marketing of products. These industries include the power industry, iron and steel, non-ferrous metals, non-metals, construction materials, finished products, metal-processing, chemical industry, and lumber and wood industries. Failures in these areas have had an overall effect on other sectors as they provide inputs for production. For instance, Zimbabwe, once the bread basket of southern Africa, had reduced scope of agricultural production. Here also lies a problem of assessing the impact. The correlation between sanctions and failed agricultural production is

strong but some attribute it mainly to the failed fast track land reform.

For the general populace, sanctions heavily impacted on the life and health of the civilian population. Zimbabwe relies largely on import medicine and hospital equipment. Because of failure to get balance of payment support, the health sector was hit hard. Thus, coupled with inflation, many people could not afford hospital fees or consulting private doctors. According to Hondora (2005), [if it were not for] ZIDERA, Zimbabwe would have been able to negotiate with the IMF with a view to reschedule or cancel its debt payment, or apply for more finance. Despite the fact that Zimbabwe was already in difficulties was apparent, withdrawal of the multilateral financial institutions from providing balance of payments support to Zimbabwe has also had an effect on some bilateral creditors and donors who have followed suit by either scaling down or suspending disbursements on existing loans to the government and parastatal companies (<http://www.zimdaily.com/news/117/ARTICLE/1879/2007-07-19>). Added to that is the fact that Zimbabwe had no record of failing to service its debts and was highly rated in the international financial markets. Gono (2007) has aptly captured the effects in the health sector noting:

Danida has also suspended the US\$29.7m health sector support programs established in May 2000 as a result of the land reform program. Zimbabwe's grant application for funding for its HIV/AIDS programmes to the Global Fund for AIDS was also rejected on political grounds. Three-

quarters of the equipment in hospitals in the capital, Harare, are not functional and this has had serious repercussions for the ordinary people. In the backdrop of an already overburdened health delivery system, many Zimbabweans are now finding it difficult to access affordable health facilities and drugs, particularly anti-retrovirals for HIV/AIDS patients. The City of Harare's Health Department immensely benefited from the various joint research projects with international stakeholders. These projects have since been terminated. The department used to benefit from such projects as, after their completion, it took over the equipment used for the research projects. The sanctions have also indirectly resulted in the relocation of the World Health Organization's regional offices to Congo Brazzaville, accompanied by retrenchment of Zimbabweans formerly employed by the WHO.

In as far as investment is concerned, in a situation where the capital account is in deficit, international investors, naturally, prefer other countries for investment, and this has deprived Zimbabwe of much-needed foreign direct investment (FDI). On the domestic front the negative perceptions by the international community led to Zimbabwean companies to access lines of credit to prop up their investment. According to Gono (2007):

As a result, our companies have to pay cash for imports. Also as a result of the risk premium, the country's private companies have been securing offshore funds at prohibitive interest rates. This has had a ripple

effect on employment levels and low capacity utilization as reflected by shortages of basic goods and services. Declining export performance has also adversely affected the standards of living for the general populace, and because of the deteriorating economic conditions, the country has experienced large-scale emigration, especially of skilled labour, thus further straining the economy. The sanctions have adversely impacted on FDI to Zimbabwe. Investors are shying away and FDI inflows have collapsed from US\$444.3m in 1998 to US\$50m in 2006. In addition, Anglo-American companies have been strongly discouraged from investing in Zimbabwe by their home governments.

Individual countries' withdrawal of support negatively impacted on a number of sectors. In the field of agriculture, Danida had been supporting Zimbabwe's agricultural sector programme, but its withdrawal plunged the country into food insecurity. In the education sector the Swedish government stopped its support programme in 2000. It used to facilitate the supply of textbooks, special education needs and construction of school buildings. As a result, the universities were severely affected as they could not access computers and related accessories from American IT companies (<http://www.zimdaily.com/news/117/ARTICLE/1879/2007-07-19>).

In the transport sector, Zimbabwe used to have a transport sector support programme of US\$48m, from Danida, which was started in April 2000. As Gono (2007) observes:

Had this program been undertaken to completion, it could have created employment opportunities and enhanced trade through efficient

movement of commodities within the country and the region... This was [also] meant to enhance entrepreneurial skills and capacity building for the rural population. However, no new programs have been put in place because of Sweden's suspension of cooperation with Zimbabwe.

It is important to highlight at this juncture that it is very difficult to make an accurate assessment of the impact of sanctions as it needs to take into consideration the environment in which the sanction regime operated as well as several other factors that should be factored in in the assessment. According to McGee (2007), two challenges often emerge:

The first is in determining the current status of humanitarian conditions in the sanctioned country or region, in the midst of a complex and often rapidly changing political and security environment. The second is in distinguishing between the effects of sanctions and the effects of other factors that influence the humanitarian situation in the targeted country.

Firstly, Zimbabwe was already undergoing a downturn if one was to trace its history from independence, and the situation was by now deteriorating— sanctions or no sanctions. Zimbabwean economy was going to suffer or, in essence, the political and economic environment which existed was not conducive to development cooperation. In other words, the problems cited may not be as a result of sanctions, especially taking the issue of food shortage. According to White (2007) it was as a result of IMF's earlier policies in Zimbabwe. She remarks:

Zimbabwe had always been a surplus maize producer with stockpiles of more than 1 million tons to tide the country over drought years. After implementing the structural adjustment plan(s) of the World Bank...which forced the government of Zimbabwe to sell its stockpiles of maize to make a profit so as to pay IMF and World Bank debt..... Zimbabwe now has to import maize to feed its destitute population. The IMF and World Bank structural adjustment plan(s) have precipitated food shortages in Zimbabwe, for which the ZANU-PF government is being blamed. These food shortages (read: famine) are part of the excuses used by the U.S. and EU to sanction Zimbabwe. Furthermore, the IMF and World Bank structural adjustment plan(s) devastated the economy of the South African country of Zimbabwe.

Secondly, a sanctioned state will design coping mechanisms that may help to mitigate or shift the impact of sanctions. Faced with problems, most of the time governments, industries and citizens have ways of shifting resources and activities to circumvent the restrictions that sanctions at first impose. In the framework of government and industries, a new policy, dubbed the "Look East" policy, that made strides in mitigating adverse effects of the sanctions was crafted. At individual levels, various household survival strategies were developed to ensure that they survive the adverse impacts.

Finally, other states and private actors interested in maintaining trade and other commercial ties with regimes that are subject to sanctions are not likely to support trade bans against states that would affect their business. In addition, the af-

affected states and individuals may resort to other trading partners that are not part of the trade regime. As such, Zimbabwe, faced with adverse reactions from the West, reformulated its policies and looked east. Some international actors that find themselves failing to access markets might find this as the window of opportunity to do business, thereby making the sanction regime fail.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, sanctions as a tool in international relations have had problems in meeting their objective and have worked successfully only in a minority of cases. The Zimbabwean case seems to demonstrate the same. The theoretical basis of sanctions is that they compel the government of the target country to change its approach in relation to certain problematic issues. For Zimbabwe, it has been done not only in the pretext of targeted sanctions on certain individuals in leadership posts as conventional wisdom seeks to imply, but in a manner that also had overall bearing on the general populace. We conclude that the success of sanctions largely depends on how morally and value sound they are seen from the perspective of the imposers as well as the target and the intended beneficiaries. Failure to appeal to the intended beneficiaries as the Zimbabwean case demonstrates, makes the aims and objective of

the sanctions regime dysfunctional. On the other hand, the target can institute measures to circumvent the negative effects of sanctions making assessment of the impact largely problematic.

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